

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“HOW TO PREVENT CONFLICT IN AN ORGANIZATION”

If you look at the meaning of the word conflict in the dictionary, you may find it is a struggle for power, property, and others. Why do people struggle for power? Is it because of envy or simply a defense mechanism to hide their insecurities and foolishness? People were born good and moral. They become vicious only because some situations trigger them to act that way. Why do they act that way if they can discern right and wrong? Another definition of conflict is, that it is also a strong disagreement between people. Conflict is unavoidable in an organization. In every organization, it is always present. It may be between the boss and the employee or between the employees. It gives spice to the relationships of the people inside it. If it is unavoidable, is there a way how it will be handled or solved? Here are some tips on how to solve organizational conflicts:

1. **Communication:** Every minute of our lives, we communicate to express our ideas, feelings, opinions, and perceptions about something. However, many people might misinterpret what we are saying. It is therefore necessary for us to communicate well our thoughts so that we will not be misinterpreted by others. If we offend someone, we should communicate with that person and explain our side precisely. Nonetheless, the offender should have an open mind to accept the explanation and forgive as soon as possible.
2. **Order:** We should learn to do our part orderly or systematically as a member of an organization. If we focus on our own life and work, we can prevent conflict from occurring. Sometimes conflicts arise because we meddle in one's business. Let's mind our own business. Let us do our job excellently by performing it more than what is expected of us.
3. **Organize:** Learning to organize ourselves by arranging our priorities can help us to avoid conflicts. Likewise, we accomplish first the most important task down to the not-that-valuable or nonsense tasks. Knowing our priorities can help us become more productive and efficient members of the organization.
4. **Listen:** We sometimes reply immediately without understanding what the speaker is saying. We should not be incessantly talking if we don't have yet an understanding of the message. Our words are powerful. They can ruin lives and relationships. They are the most powerful agents that can stop a war, break a heart, and kill people. We should be an active listener for us to weigh if we have to speak out about something or just keep it on our own.

We have to realize that we are not in the organization to create conflict. We are there to perform duties and roles that are on our shoulders. Let's remember that we should always maintain peace and harmony in an organization by being C-O-O-L.